

Voicing the Voiceless: Language and Silence as the Strategies of Resistance in the works of Mahashweta Devi and Vijay Tendulkar

Riddhi Mahindra

Amity School of Languages

Riddhimahindra3@gmail.com

1. Abstract

This research paper looks at how Mahashweta Devi and Vijay Tendulkar showcase women in their works and how they resist the unfair treatment done by the society using both speech and silence. Their works “The Hunt”, “The Breastgiver” and *Silence! The Court is in Session* explores how women struggles against patriarchy, caste and class oppression. Mahashweta Devi shows both language and silence as the strategies of resistance in her works and Vijay Tendulkar shows how society tries to silent women and uses their words against them. Through this study, it becomes clear that how both the writers give space to women’s struggles and showcase the harsh reality of women life, and how they are resisting in their own ways.

Keywords: Patriarchy, women struggle, language, silence, Mahashweta Devi, Vijay Tendulkar.

2. Introduction

Mahashweta Devi and Vijay Tendulkar are the important writers of Indian literature who writes boldly about the struggles of women in the society. Mahashweta was an Indian Bengali writer whose focus was on social injustice, exploitation, resistance particularly against communities like Adivasis and Dalit women. Her ideology made her write about gender inequality and class discrimination. Through her stories she focused on how women were oppressed in the society. Mahashweta Devi was not just a writer but a fighter for justice. She through her stories brings attention to the pain and silence of tribal people and poor. On the other hand, Vijay Tendulkar who was a Marathi playwright he wrote about social issues, exposed urban patriarchy, middle class hypocrisy known for showing the condition of women. His plays show strong female characters who are known to fight in complex ways. He was a bold Indian playwright who wrote plays that exposed the dark side of power, patriarchy and social rules. In his works, silence and language are not just part of the story, they are weapons. He used theatre to challenge society and show hidden struggles of individuals. He believed that theatre should reflect society honestly, even if the truth is uncomfortable. His works remain important even today because it questions the way society treats women, the other or the powerless.

Both writers focus on female struggles faced due to patriarchy, caste and class but still they find the way to resist these challenges. Sometimes the women in the stories are found speaking up for themselves and sometimes in complete silence which also is a symbol of strong resistance. This research paper studies how both the writers give voice to women and

show how silence and language both can be the powerful tool of resistance in the society which tries to suppress women.

Analysis of the works

The Hunt

It is a story about a tribal woman Mary Oraon, shown as strong, independent woman who resists exploitation and oppression around her. It shows how she chose violence to protect herself from Collector Singh. In this story it can be seen how Mahashweta devi have tried to show that a woman can fight back in a society that tries to silent her. For instance, when Prasadji's wife talks to Mary about her marriage she bluntly says that "Why? Will you organize my marriage" (Devi,76). This shows that Mahashweta Devi has made her protagonist bold, who loves to live her life at her own terms, this also shows the use of language as resistance. She further says, "The Muslim says he will marry me, but your brother only wanted to keep me" (Devi,76). This shows she doesn't like to be treated as an object and wants to live on her own terms and doesn't want anybody to control her life. Another instance is when Mary goes to the village with Mrs. Prasadji and people call her "Mussulman's chick" to which she boldly replies that "Would you marry me?" (Devi,77) through these fearless words, she refuses to let their taunts control her. Her speech again becomes the tool of resistance of the oppression which villagers tried to do to Mary, but she instead gives a fearless answer and is also determined to marry Jalim. This shows the powerful way of Mahashweta Devi of trying to resist the unwanted voices that try to silence Mary. Mary not only uses her voice for herself but also for the people around her, For Instance when Collector Singh tries to exploit the people of Kuruda by giving them less

wages for their labor, she exposes his injustice by saying “Twelve annas and eight annas, no porter carries gentlemen’s cases for this price”(Devi,79) which shows she tried to reveal the true face of the broker and also shows that she uses her courage and protects the people of her community from exploitation. Through this it is seen that the voice becomes the tool of resistance for the collective and can protect them from the exploitation done by society.

Furthermore, Mary is not scared to confront those who mistreat or flirt with her, she knows how to protect her boundaries. For example, when Collector Singh tries to cross his boundaries with her, she bluntly replies that “Brokers like you with tight pants and dark glasses are ten a rupee on the streets of Tohri”. (Devi,79), by saying this she openly insults Collector Singh this shows she is not scared of anyone, even if it is high caste men standing in front of her. She boldly speaks whatever she feels like. She didn’t even fear her landlord’s son Banwari and never resist any insult through silence, she always learned to has speak up for herself. She understands the people around her see her illegitimate, white daughter and mistreat her. She says to him this shows that she is never scared of anyone and lives a fearless life and knows how to protect herself. Significantly, Mahashweta Devi further shows the bold spirit of Mary when Collector Singh, a lustful broker, tries to come close to her and to take advantage of her, she refuses to be a victim. She tells him “I’ll make up for everything, at the day of spring festival.” (Devi,82). This shows that she cleverly tries to manipulate him and courageously hunt him by killing him with the Machete. This shows that she is not scared to anyone, and she refuses to be a victim of exploitation and knows how to stand for herself.

This story represents how Devi portrays women as independent, fearless and how she refuses the character to be silent and uses language and action as a tool of resistance. The author in

the story has conveyed the message through the character of Mary that women should raise voice and strike back for their rights and dignity. She has proved that subaltern women know how to speak for the injustice using language and strategies to reclaim their rights in society.

The Breastgiver

In the Breastgiver, the focus shifts to the silent endurance of Jashoda who sees herself as a devoted wife and gives her all to feed her family, she is a symbol of exploitation faced by the women within the family and the society. She dedicated her life for feeding countless children in society. She is exploited by everyone, her family and society. Mahashweta Devi shows that women's roles are taken for granted, leading to the exploitation. Jashoda becomes silent, which exposes the harsh reality of patriarchal society and economic oppression. For instance, when Jasoda was breastfeeding the babies endlessly which says as "Jashoda became vocal and constantly suckling the infants." (Devi,222-256) this shows that she became the symbol of endless giving to society, without being vocal about it. First, she remained silent and accepted her duty as a mother, but then constantly suckling shows the dependence of society and selfishness. Through Jashoda Mahashweta Devi shows that silence can also become the language of resistance when women represent the exploitation done on her by the society. Furthermore, while Jashoda had to constantly suck the infants, the shift occurs when she finally confronts her husband Kangali at the temple "You've saved everything and eaten the food that sucked by body" (Devi,8). She finally understood that her lifelong service and devotion was one sided and how her family was ungrateful of her service. This vital point shows that Jashoda finally spoke of the exploitation done to her by society to her husband. In

this moment, it shows that even the subaltern being silent throughout the story can speak up when its height of exploitation, this moment shows her anger and exposes the hypocrisy of society. Moreover, she was scattered when she came to know that she is useless in Kangali's life and he doesn't care anymore. Furthermore, when she got to know that Kangali said to Nabin that "Don't talk to me, about her anymore". (Devi, 10) this broke her heart into pieces. This shows the harsh reality of patriarchal society that they only see women as an object and treats her accordingly and, they don't even feel grateful for all the sacrifices and exploitation she has been through, to feed her family. This is the powerful symbol of patriarchy, which shows how her husband doesn't want to be with her, when she needs him the most. After being heartbroken by his husband, she now understands that no one will understand her now, and she chose to be silent through from inside she was all into pieces, but she remained silent. What deepens the tragedy of Jashoda was when her husband who was she faithful to, rejected her when doctor said, "Jashoda wouldn't last" (Devi,12) this puts him take her out of his mind painlessly, which shows that he abandons her, when she needs him the most. She becomes silent, and her silence is a metaphor of her family distanced herself themselves from her, this shows that they only saw Jashoda as an object, and her whole identity was her breast, once they become functionless, she became invisible figure in her family and society.

Mahashweta Devi's highlights the brutal reality of how women's bodies are exploited by the society, showcasing silence as the act of resistance. This shows that Jashoda compromised herself for her family but at the end it was all worthless because all that she faced at last was abandonment from the family and society. Mahashweta Devi uses silence and Jashoda's

speaking to show that women fight for themselves even in situations where society forgets to give them the care and respect, they deserve.

Silence! The Court Is in Session

In this play Vijay Tendulkar critiques social standards regarding women sexuality, individual freedom. Leela Benare, who is the protagonist of the play, is being judged ruthlessly in the mock court session for her personal life. The play moves from lighthearted mockery to intense psychological drama. Ms. Benare is a teacher, unmarried, bearing an illegitimate child. Vijay Tendulkar shows Leela Benare as a strong, independent and bold woman. In the early on the play, it is seeing Leela Benare saying “I’ll do what I like with myself and my life”(Vijay, 58) It shows that she wants to live life at her own terms, and it also shows she is openly speaks about her life expectations and doesn’t scare to tell what she wants in her life. Through her speech she speaks openly clearly and fearlessly to resist patriarchal oppression and assert her individuality. Moreover, Leela Benare says, “It’s my own life. It must be. It’s a very very important thing” (Vijay,61) which demonstrates she is a freedom lover and desires to live at her own terms. She refuses to confine herself to the opinions of others. Despite all the patriarchal expectations, she challenges them by voicing her opinions and making it clear that she will not conform to oppressive standards. In the play we can see Ms. Benare was being bold enough to take a stand for herself, as when they were taking her personal life as the hot topic she refused but no one listened, they were making the scenario that she had intimacy with Mr. Damle, but she took stand, by saying “It reveals nothing of the sort! Tomorrow I may be seen in our principal’s office”. (Vijay,41) this can be seen as the

representation emphasized that her presence with Mr. Damle should not be misinterpreted as evidence of intimacy. This becomes bold assertion for her dignity in so called “game”.

Benare also speaks up by saying “If anyone says one word after this, I’ll go away” (Vijay, 45). The resistant becomes more evident when Benare says that “You all have deliberately ganged up on me”. (Vijay,47), when she found out that it is not an innocent rehearsal, but an attack on her personal life. This makes her feel choked and overwhelmed, though her colleagues deny their intentions, their action says something else. Benare’s language becomes the tool of resistance she stands for the injustice done on her by exposing the hypocrisy. This shows how Tendulkar represents that her language becomes a weapon for Ms. Benare, for standing against patriarchal society. Through this Tendulkar showcases that language is more important to fight oppression of society. Then comes a point where she uses silence as a protective mechanism as she says, “Storms raged, I shut my lips tight.” (Vijay,116) It shows that her silence was not her weakness, but a way for her survival in patriarchal society. Through the silence also exposes the expectations of society from women to stay silent in betrayal and sufferings without protest. Tendulkar critiques the societal structure that forces women into suppression.

Vijay Tendulkar through Benare’s character reveals that women are often silenced and betrayal, while them believe that speaking out is revolutionary in the world, where they demand silence from women. Her language and silence are not merely forms of expressions but the essential tools for speaking up for women in an unjust society.

3. Comparative study of both the writers

Mahashweta Devi uses language as a tool of resistance in her works of *The Hunt*, she showcased Mary Oraon as a bold, independent woman, who has shown to reverse gender roles. She not only protects herself from the broker but also her village people, by showing the real face of the broker. She showcased her protection with the help of her actions. She is also seen as quick-witted to protect herself from collector Singh as when he catches her, she tells him “Not today, Today I am Unclean” (Devi,82) and protects herself from Collector Singh. Also, in the *Breastgiver* Mahashweta Devi depicts Jashoda as a devoted wife who gives her all to feed her family, but in this she couldn’t speak much about her problems. She suffers a lot internally while continuously feeding the children. She is a symbol of how society expects women to serve endlessly without complaints, and her silence is a prove of how patriarchy exploits women bodies, her silence is a critique to patriarchy. On the other hand, Vijay Tendulkar showcased her protagonist Leela Benare as one who spoke boldly, she says “what’s wrong if a woman’s life is her own? What’s wrong if she wants to live her own way”. (Vijay ,65) She tries to challenge patriarchy through speech but was silenced by society. She is seen bold initially Benare’s silence is a symbol how society forces the women to silence, using language as a form of violence.

Both showcase women resisting patriarchy but through different ways. They show that language can challenge patriarchy, but silence too can critique it, reviling the different ways through which women resist.

4. Conclusion

This research paper explores how Mahashweta Devi and Vijay Tendulkar portray women and in patriarchal society using language and silence. Mahashweta Devi's protagonist (Mary) shows how language and violence can protect you from exploitation. Mary's quick-witted, bold, independent nature is a symbol of power, while Jashoda's silence is a critique to society that exploits women's bodies. In addition, Vijay Tendulkar's protagonist Leela Benare as initially she boldly asserts her right to live life, however as the play continues, she was enforced to silence. Through these texts, it shows the complex realities of women struggles. Ultimately both writers use female protagonist to expose patriarchy and to emphasize courage, resilience of women.

In the writings silence and speech are not just expressions they are tools of power, pain and resistance. Both writers bring the struggle of women who are often silenced by the society. Through their stories they remind us that language is not just about speaking, it's about being heard, about expressing pain, truth, and courage. Even in silence, there is meaning and even in struggle, there is strength. Through their works we come face to face with the harsh realities of those who silenced by society. so, the stories do light a spark, a hope for a change, a hope that one day every voice will be free to speak without fear and maybe, that's where true resistance begins.

Works cited

- www.scribd.com/document/Silence/the/court/is/in/session.
- Devi, Mahasweta. *Imaginary Maps*. Translated by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, Routledge, 1995.
- Devi, Mahasweta. *Breast Stories*. Translated by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, Seagull Books, 1997.
- Spivak, Gayatri Chakravorty. "Can the Subaltern Speak?" *Colonial Discourse and Post-Colonial Theory: A Reader*, edited by Patrick Williams and Laura Chrisman, Columbia University Press, 1994, pp. 66-111.
- Tendulkar, Vijay. *Silence! The Court is in Session*. Oxford University Press, 1978.
- Nandy, Ashis. "Final Encounter: The Politics of the Assassination of Gandhi." *At the Edge of Psychology: Essays in Politics and Culture*, Oxford University Press, 1980, pp. 70-98